

Synthesis of Bitetralonyl and Bianthronyl Derivatives from Biphenyl Derivatives

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Succinoylation of 2,2'- and 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl with succinic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene has furnished 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'- and 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl respectively. These have been reduced and cyclised to 7,7'-dimethoxy- and 5,5'-dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl respectively. 2,2'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on Friedel-Crafts' phthaloylation yields 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(*o*-carboxybenzoyl)biphenyl which has been reduced and cyclised to 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthronyl.

Baddar and co-workers¹ studied succinoylation of 2,2'- and 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl with one mole of succinic anhydride and its methyl derivatives and isolated the mono-ketonic acid derivatives. Friedel-Crafts' phthaloylation of 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl, carried out by Scholl and co-workers², provided demethylated di-ketonic acid derivative. As a part of our studies on biphenyls, it was thought of interest to study succinoylation of 2,2'- and 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyls and phthaloylation of 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl with a view to synthesising bitetralonyl and bianthronyl derivatives.

4,4'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on Friedel-Crafts' succinoylation with 2.2 moles of succinic anhydride at the room temperature yielded 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl (Ia) which on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate afforded the known 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid³, as proved by direct comparison with the product obtained on oxidation of the dimethyl ether of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl⁴ with alkaline potassium permanganate. The di-ketonic acid on the Clemmensen reduction furnished 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-di-(γ -carboxybutyl)biphenyl which on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid provided 5,5'-dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl (IIa).

2,2'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on Friedel-Crafts' succinoylation with an excess of succinic anhydride yielded 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl (Ib). It provided the known 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate, proved by direct comparison with the product obtained according to Mathai and Sethna³. The above di-ketonic acid on the Clemmensen reduction furnished 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(γ -carboxybutyl)biphenyl. Cyclisation of the above acid with polyphosphoric acid took place at 6,6'-positions, giving rise to 7,7'-dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl (IIb). On reduction by the Huang-Minlon method⁵, it afforded 7,7'-dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralyl which on aromatisation with selenium dioxide furnished the known 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-binaphthyl⁶, as confirmed by direct comparison with the product obtained

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2199.

2. *Monatsh.*, 1921, 41, 583.

3. *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 347.

4. Boon-Long, *J. Pharm. Assoc. Siam.*, 1948, 1, No. 4, 5; *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 5017.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2487.

6. Ostermayer, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2454.

by the oxidative coupling of β -naphthol with ferric chloride and subsequent methylation of the 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl formed with dimethyl sulphate.

Baddar *et al.* have reported succinylation of 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl with one mole of succinic anhydride in nitrobenzene. They obtained an acid, m.p. 229-30°, for which they suggested the β -4-methoxy-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)benzoylpropionic acid structure on the basis of the analysis agreeing with one mole of acetic acid of crystallisation and of oxidation of the acid with 10% sodium hypobromite solution to an acid presumed to be 4-methoxy-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)benzoic acid (m.p. 334-36°). The said acid was prepared for comparison by the crossed Ullmann reaction between methyl 3-iodo-4-methoxybenzoate and *o*-iodo-anisole with copper bronze at 230-35° and subsequent hydrolysis of the ester. It is now found that the ketonic acid, m.p. 229-30°, reported by Baddar *et al.*, is 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl, described above. Friedel-Crafts' succinylation of 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl with one mole of succinic anhydride afforded a ketonic acid (A), m.p. 162°, analysis of which fitted a mono-ketonic acid derivative and which on further succinylation with an excess of succinic anhydride furnished 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl, described above. Hence the acid (A) must be β -4-methoxy-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)benzoylpropionic acid.

[a: R=OMe; R'=H. b: R=H; R'=OMe]

2,2'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on the Friedel-Crafts phthaloylation with phthalic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene at the room temperature provided 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(*o*-carboxybenzoyl)biphenyl(III). Cyclisation of the above acid with sulphuric acid or polyphosphoric acid was not successful. It was therefore reduced by the Clemmensen method to 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(*o*-carboxybenzyl)biphenyl and then cyclised to 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthronyl(IV) which on oxidation with sodium dichromate in acetic acid yielded the known 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthraquinonyl⁷, as proved by direct comparison.

*EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for Friedel-Crafts' Succinoylation and Phthaloylation.—To a mixture of anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.04 *M*) and dry nitrobenzene (50 ml), kept below 10° in a r.b flask, finely powdered anhydride (0.02*M*) and the biphenyl derivative (0.01*M*) were added. The flask was well protected from moisture and kept for 48 hr. at the room temperature with occasional stirring. It was then poured on crushed ice containing HCl. The product obtained after removal of nitrobenzene was repeatedly treated with hot water till freed of unchanged acid and then crystallised from ethyl acetate or acetic acid. For the preparation of 4-methoxy-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)benzoylpropionic acid, anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.02*M*) and succinic anhydride (0.01*M*) were used (Table I).

TABLE I

No.	Name.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	4,4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl	187°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₈	C : 64.1% H : 5.6	63.8% 5.3
2	2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl	230°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₈	C : 63.8 H : 5.1	63.8 5.3
3	β -4-Methoxy-3-(<i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl)benzoylpropionic acid	162°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅	C : 68.5 H : 5.8	68.8 5.7
4	2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(<i>o</i> -carboxybenzoyl) biphenyl	255°	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₈	C : 70.4 H : 4.6	70.6 4.3

Clemmensen Reduction of the Ketonic Acids.—To the ketonic acid (1 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), zinc amalgam (5 g.) was added. HCl was then added to the mixture portionwise, heated on a steam bath for 8 hr., and filtered hot. On dilution, the reduced acid obtained was crystallised from dilute ethanol or acetic acid (Table II).

TABLE II

No.	Name	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	4,4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-di-(γ -carboxybutyl)biphenyl	185°	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 68.1% H : 6.8	68.4% 6.7
2	2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(γ -carboxybutyl)biphenyl	155°	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 68.1 H : 6.9	68.4 6.7
4	2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(<i>o</i> -carboxybenzyl)biphenyl	220°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 74.6 H : 5.4	74.6 5.4

Cyclisation of the Reduced Acids.—The reduced acid (1 g.) was mixed with polyphosphoric acid (20 ml) and the mixture heated over a water bath at 75-85° for 4 hr. Alternatively, the ketonic acid was mixed with 95% H₂SO₄ (20 ml) and kept for 30 min. In both the cases, on dilution with water, the cyclised product was obtained and it was crystallised from benzene or glacial acetic acid (Table III).

*All melting points are uncorrected.

In the case of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di-(*o*-carboxybenzyl)biphenyl, polyphosphoric acid was found to be ineffective for cyclisation. When the reaction time was increased, some undesirable products were formed.

TABLE III

No.	Name.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	5,5'-Dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl	211°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄	C : 75.7% H : 6.3	75.4% 6.3
2	7,7'-Dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl	187°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄	C : 75.5 H : 6.2	75.4 6.3
4	2,2'-Dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthranyl	263°	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	C : 80.8 H : 5.0	80.7 4.9

Oxidation of the Ketonic Acids.—To the ketonic acid (1 g.), dissolved in alkali (10%, 10 ml), KMnO₄ (3 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed gently over a sand bath for 4 hr. After cooling, the excess of permanganate was removed by adding sodium sulphite and the reaction mixture was filtered. The filtrate on acidification provided the acid which was crystallised from acetic acid.

6,6'-*Dimethoxy-5,5'-bitetralyl.*—To 7,7'-dimethoxy-8,8'-bitetralonyl (1 g.), dissolved in glycol (30 ml), hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed on a wire gauze for 10 hr. It was cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated bitetralyl was crystallised from petroleum in cubes, m.p. 116°.

The same bitetralyl was also obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the bitetralonyl, but the yield was poor. (Found: C, 81.9; H, 8.0. C₂₂H₂₆O₂ requires C, 82.0; H, 8.1%).

2,2'-*Dimethoxy-1,1'-binaphthyl.*—To 6,6'-dimethoxy-5,5'-bitetralyl (1 g.), dissolved in amyl alcohol (15 ml), powdered selenium dioxide (5 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed in an oil bath for 10 hr. and then filtered hot. 2,2'-Dimethoxy-1,1'-binaphthyl, obtained after removal of the solvent, was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 6.0. C₂₂H₁₈O₂ requires C, 84.1; H, 5.7%).

The same binaphthyl derivative was also obtained by methylation of 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the former was 195° (Ostermayer⁶ reported m.p. 190°)

2,2'-*Dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthraquinonyl.*—2,2'-Dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthranyl (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 ml); powdered sodium dichromate (10 g.) was added to it and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 4 hr. On pouring the mixture into water, the precipitated product was crystallised from nitrobenzene in long yellow needles, m.p. 345°. It is insoluble in sodium hydroxide and exhibits no colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 3.8. C₃₀H₁₈O₆ requires C, 75.9; H, 3.8%).

The same bianthraquinonyl was prepared for comparison according to the method of Haller and Perkin⁷ with slight modification as follows.

2-Methyl-1-bromoanthraquinone, obtained by brominating 2-hydroxyanthraquinone with one mole of bromine in NaOH and subsequent methylation with dimethyl sulphate, was refluxed with copper bronze in diphenyl ether. The mixture was filtered hot and on cooling, yellow needles of 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-bianthraquinonyl were obtained; m.p and mixed m.p. with the former was not depressed.

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